

Appendix B

Additional information on the participants

In this section participants' differences in central characteristics are analyzed.

Differences in central characteristics between experimental conditions

Age. An one-way ANOVA indicated that the experimental conditions did not differ significantly in age, $F(3, 513) = 0.95, p = .418, \eta^2 = .01$. Descriptive statistics of age within and across experimental conditions are presented in table B1.

Table B1

Descriptive statistics of age

	Crisis responsibility				Σ	
	High ($n = 262$)		Low ($n = 255$)		$(n = 517)$	
Framing	<i>M</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>M</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>M</i>	<i>SD</i>
Humorous ($n = 250$)	42.74	15.77	42.45	15.47	42.60	15.60
Rational ($n = 267$)	43.85	16.14	45.45	16.42	44.67	16.27
Σ ($n = 517$)	43.30	15.93	44.05	16.02	43.67	15.97

Note. Means and standard deviations for age graded by both manipulated factors (i.e., crisis responsibility (high vs. low) and framing of the crisis response strategy (humorous vs. rational)) and across conditions (Σ).

Sex. The two-sided Fisher's Exact test indicated the experimental conditions did not differ significantly in sex, $p = .829$. The frequency distribution is displayed in table B2.

Table B2

Differences between experimental conditions in sex

	Sex				row total
	male	female	divers	not specified	
HH	68 51.91%	61 46.57%	0 0.00%	2 1.53%	131 25.34%
HR	75 57.25%	55 41.99%	1 0.76%	0 0.00%	131 25.34%
LH	61 51.26%	56 47.06%	1 0.84%	1 0.84%	119 23.02%
LR	68 50.00%	64 47.06%	2 1.47%	2 1.47%	136 26.31%
column total	272 52.61%	236 45.65%	4 0.77%	5 0.97%	517 100.00%

Note. HH = high crisis responsibility – humorous framing; HR = high crisis responsibility – rational framing; LH = low crisis responsibility – humorous framing; LR = low crisis responsibility – rational framing.

Education. The two-sided Fisher's Exact test indicated that the experimental groups differed significantly in education, $p = .016$. The frequency distribution is displayed in table B3.

Table B3*Differences between experimental conditions in education*

	Education									Row total
	NSC	LSC	GCSE	SA	A	CD	UD	D	OSC	
HH	0	8	12	18	33	24	35	1	0	131
	0.00%	6.11%	9.12%	13.74%	25.19%	18.32%	26.72%	0.76%	0.00%	25.34%
HR	0	5	25	6	25	36	29	4	1	131
	0.00%	3.82%	19.08%	4.58%	19.08%	27.48%	22.14%	3.05%	0.76%	25.34%
LH	0	5	17	6	27	20	36	7	1	119
	0.00%	4.20%	14.29%	5.04%	22.69%	16.81%	30.25%	5.88%	0.84%	23.02%
LR	0	5	13	18	24	26	41	5	4	136
	0.00%	3.68%	9.56%	13.24%	17.65%	19.12%	30.15%	3.68%	2.94%	26.31%
column total	0	23	67	48	109	106	141	17	6	517
	0.00%	4.45%	12.96%	9.28%	21.08%	20.50%	27.27%	3.29%	1.16%	100.00%

Note. HH = high crisis responsibility – humorous framing; HR = high crisis responsibility – rational framing; LH = low crisis responsibility – humorous framing; LR = low crisis responsibility – rational framing; NSC = no school leaving certificate; LSC = lower secondary school leaving certificate; GCSE = GCSE O-levels; SA = specialized A-levels; A = A-levels; CD = college of higher education degree; UD = university degree; D = doctorate; OSC = other school leaving certificate.

Working areas. The two-sided Fisher's Exact tests indicated that the experimental conditions did not differ significantly in their working areas, all $ps > .05$. The frequency distribution of each working area is displayed in table B4.

Table B4
Differences between experimental conditions in working areas

	Working areas		Row total
	Outside local government	Local government	
HH	115	16	131
	87.79%	12.21%	25.34%
HR	121	10	131
	92.37%	7.63%	25.34%
LH	106	13	119
	89.08%	10.92%	23.02%
LR	128	8	136
	94.12%	5.88%	26.31%
column total	470	47	517
	90.91%	9.09%	100.00%
	Outside crisis management	Crisis management	
HH	123	8	131
	93.89%	6.11%	25.34%
HR	126	5	131
	96.18%	3.82%	25.34%
LH	111	8	119
	93.28%	6.72%	23.02%
LR	129	7	136
	94.85%	5.15%	26.31%
column total	489	28	517
	94.58%	5.41%	100.00%
	Outside FBRSTHW	FBRSTHW	
HH	83	48	131
	63.36%	36.64%	25.34%
HR	86	45	131
	65.65%	34.35%	25.34%
LH	79	40	119
	66.39%	33.61%	23.02%
LR	89	47	136
	65.44%	34.56%	26.31%
column total	337	180	517
	65.18%	34.82%	100.00%
	Outside police	Police	
HH	125	6	131
	95.42%	4.58%	25.34%
HR	127	4	131
	96.95%	3.05%	25.34%
LH	112	7	119
	94.12%	5.88%	23.02%
LR	133	3	136
	97.79%	2.21%	26.31%
column total	497	20	517
	96.13%	3.87%	100.00%
	Outside named public sectors	Named public sectors	
HH	55	76	131
	41.99%	58.02%	25.34%
HR	55	76	131
	41.99%	58.02%	25.34%
LH	56	63	119
	47.06%	52.94%	23.02%
LR	52	84	136
	38.24%	61.77%	26.31%
column total	218	299	517
	42.17%	57.83%	100.00%

Note. HH = high crisis responsibility – humorous framing; HR = high crisis responsibility – rational framing; LH = low crisis responsibility – humorous framing; LR = low crisis responsibility – rational framing; FBRSTHW = Fire brigade, rescue service, THW, disaster control; police = police or security authorities

Further control variables. An one-way ANOVA indicated that the experimental conditions did not differ significantly in disposition to trust, $F(3, 513) = 1.02, p = .384, \eta^2 = .01$. However, the one-way ANOVA showed that the experimental conditions differed significantly in sense of humor, $F(3, 513) = 3.91, p = .009, \eta^2 = .02$. Descriptive data of disposition to trust and sense of humor are displayed in table B5 and B6, respectively.

Table B5

Descriptive statistics of disposition to trust

	Crisis responsibility				Σ ($n = 517$)	
	High ($n = 262$)		Low ($n = 255$)			
Framing	<i>M</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>M</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>M</i>	<i>SD</i>
Humorous ($n = 250$)	3.58	0.78	3.67	0.72	3.62	0.75
Rational ($n = 267$)	3.73	0.73	3.62	0.76	3.67	0.75
Σ ($n = 517$)	3.65	0.76	3.64	0.74	3.65	0.75

Note. Means and standard deviations for disposition to trust graded by both manipulated factors (i.e., crisis responsibility (high vs. low) and framing of the crisis response strategy (humorous vs. rational)) and across conditions (Σ).

Table B6

Descriptive statistics of sense of humor

	Crisis responsibility				Σ ($n = 517$)	
	High ($n = 262$)		Low ($n = 255$)			
Framing	<i>M</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>M</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>M</i>	<i>SD</i>
Humorous ($n = 250$)	9.40	1.50	9.28	1.62	9.34	1.55
Rational ($n = 267$)	8.82	1.69	8.95	1.54	8.88	1.61
Σ ($n = 517$)	9.11	1.62	9.10	1.58	9.11	1.60

Note. Average sum value and its standard deviations for sense of humor graded by both manipulated factors (i.e., crisis responsibility (high vs. low) and framing of the crisis response strategy (humorous vs. rational)) and across conditions (Σ).

Differences in central characteristics between participants and excluded persons

Age. Participants were on average 43.09 years old ($SD = 15.76$) while excluded person were 37.50 years old ($SD = 14.00$). A Wilcoxon signed-rank test indicated that participants and excluded persons did not differ significantly in age, $Z = 2010, p = .273$.

Sex. The two-sided Fisher’s Exact test indicated that participants and excluded participants did not differ significantly in sex, $p = .602$. The frequency distribution is displayed in table B7.

Table B7

Differences between participants and excluded persons in sex

	Sex				row total
	male	female	divers	Not specified	
excluded	4 40.00%	6 60.00%	0 0.00%	0 0.00%	10 1.90%
participants	272 52.61%	236 45.65%	4 0.77%	5 0.97%	517 98.10%
column total	276 52.37%	242 45.92%	4 0.76%	5 0.95%	527 100.00%

Education. The two-sided Fisher’s Exact test indicated that participants and excluded participants did not differ significantly in education, $p = .260$. The frequency distribution is displayed in table B8.

Table B8*Differences between participants and excluded persons in education*

	Education									Row total
	NSC	LSC	GCSE	SA	A	CD	UD	D	OSC	
excluded	0	0	1	0	1	2	4	1	1	10
	0.00%	0.00%	10.00%	0.00%	10.00%	20.00%	40.00%	10.00%	10.00%	1.90%
participants	0	23	67	48	109	106	141	17	6	517
	0.00%	4.45%	12.96%	9.28%	21.08%	20.50%	27.27%	3.29%	1.16%	
column total	0	23	68	48	110	108	145	18	7	527
	0.00%	4.36%	12.90%	9.11%	20.87%	20.49%	27.51%	3.52%	1.33%	100%

Note. NSC = no school leaving certificate; LSC = lower secondary school leaving certificate; GCSE = GCSE O-levels; SA = specialized A-levels; A = A-levels; CD = college of higher education degree; UD = university degree; D = doctorate; OSC = other school leaving certificate.

Working areas. The two-sided Fisher's Exact tests indicated that participants and excluded participants did not differ significantly in their working areas, all $ps > .05$. The frequency distribution of each working area is displayed in table B9.

Table B9

Differences between participants and excluded persons in working areas

	Working areas		Row total
	Outside local government	Local government	
excluded	9	1	10
	90.00%	10.00%	1.90%
participants	470	47	517
	90.91%	9.09%	98.10%
column total	479	48	527
	90.89%	9.11%	100.00%
	Outside crisis management	Crisis management	
excluded	10	0	10
	100.00%	0.00%	1.90%
participants	489	28	517
	94.58%	5.42%	98.10%
column total	499	28	527
	94.67%	5.31%	100.00%
	Outside FBRSTHW	FBRSTHW	
excluded	8	2	10
	80.00%	20.00%	1.90%
participants	337	180	517
	65.18%	34.82%	98.10%
column total	345	182	527
	65.46%	34.54%	100%
	Outside police	Police	
excluded	10	0	10
	100.00%	0.00%	1.90%
participants	497	20	517
	96.13%	3.87%	98.10%
column total	507	20	527
	96.20%	3.80%	100%
	Public sector	Outside named public sectors	
excluded	3	7	10
	30.00%	70.00%	1.90%
participants	218	299	517
	42.17%	57.83%	98.10%
column total	221	306	527
	41.94%	58.06%	100%

Note. FBRSTHW = Fire brigade, rescue service, THW, disaster control; police = police and security authorities.

Further control variables. Participants as well as excluded persons reported high levels of disposition to trust ($M_{\text{participants}} = 3.65$, $SD_{\text{participants}} = 0.75$, $M_{\text{excluded}} = 3.63$, $SD_{\text{excluded}} = 0.64$). A Wilcoxon signed-rank test indicated that they did not differ significantly in disposition to trust, $Z = 2456.5$, $p = .786$. However, participants reported higher levels of sense of humour ($M = 9.11$, $SD = 1.60$) than persons who were excluded from data analysis ($M = 8.30$, $SD = 1.57$), $Z = 1660.5$, $p = .048$.